

Winter lightning triggered by wind-turbines: the case of snowstorm Filomena

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1. ABSTRACT

Winter storm Filomena battered the Iberian Peninsula on the 9-10th January 2021, covering the eastern half of Spain with a huge amount of snow. Apart from the historical snowfall, lightning activity was observed during this snowstorm episode. Although most of lightning was oversea, lightning hotspots were observed in different regions across the Iberian Peninsula, such as Galicia, Asturias, Catalunya and Andalucía. A closer look at the inland lightning hotspots showed wind turbines in the close vicinity of most of the lightning. The analysis of the ERA5 variables has shown that environmental conditions were prone to winter lightning. One of the most representative is the height of the $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ isotherm, a key variable for cloud electrification. A low height of the $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ enhances electric fields at the top of tall man-made structures, like the wind turbines, favouring the inception of upward lightning. Moreover, moving blades are exposed to stronger local electric fields than static objects, favouring the initiation of stable lightning leaders and subsequent lightning strokes.

2. INTRODUCTION

Interest in winter lightning has grown worldwide in recent years, notably because of the global expansion of wind power generation [1,2]. Indeed, lightning is one of the major causes of severe damage to wind turbines (WT) and add a significant cost to their operation and maintenance [3,4,5]. Consequently, winter lightning has been recently introduced and conceptualized in the 2018 revision of the “Lightning Protection of Wind Turbines” standard IEC 61400-24 [2].

But what is winter lightning? In fact, the winter season only accounts for a small percentage of the annual lightning activity. This percentage is around 3% in Europe [6] and even lower for the continental U.S. (0.03%) [7]. Winter lightning is linked to a relatively uncommon weather phenomenon, the thundersnow, a snowstorm producing a low number of lightning flashes (e.g. snowstorm Filomena).

Schultz and Vavrik [8] described the ingredients necessary for snowstorm: (i) Moisture – abundant water vapour in the air to form clouds and precipitation; (ii) Lift – a mechanism to raise moist air to form clouds and precipitation; (iii) Unstable temperature profile – rapidly decreasing temperature with height, which can favour vigorous upward motion in the atmosphere; and (iv) Cold air – below-freezing temperatures within clouds and near the ground. Without cold air in these layers, precipitation would reach the surface as rain.

Besides, we should add an electrification process to the list of ingredients to have a “thundersnow”. The most widely accepted charging mechanism as the primary source of thunderstorm electrification is the non-inductive charging mechanism (NIC) [9, 10]. Basically, it states that charge is transferred during the collision of different cloud particles in an environment of moderate liquid water contents and temperatures between -10°C and -30°C . Subsequent differential separation of particles under gravity is then assumed to cause the creation of layers or regions of opposite charge [11]. Without going into details of the NIC electrification processes, a key concept is the height of -10°C temperature level. This height relates to the lower part of the main negative charge layer at moderate convection [12, 13]. It should be noted that this relationship is valid under different climatic regions, different types of storms and across the seasons [14,15]. Therefore, these environmental temperatures also apply to winter storms, which entails that cloud charges will be at lower altitudes in winter.

The practical implication of this downward translation is that man-made tall structures (power lines, wind turbines, telecommunication towers, etc.) on the ground are exposed to stronger electric fields and more hazardous lightning conditions in winter [16, 17, 18, 19, 20]. For example, Matsui et al. [21] showed that wind turbine accidents related to lightning in Japan are 47 times more frequent in winter, compared to the summer.

The term winter lightning originally referred to lightning originated in the particular winter storms of the Sea of Japan [21, 22]. Montanya et al. [23] mapped the global distribution of winter lightning, according to the following criterion: winter lightning are those occurring when temperature are equal or lower than $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the 700 hPa level. Apart from the well-known coastal areas of the Sea of Japan, the worldwide map shows other significant active areas during winter, like the north of the Mediterranean basin (especially the Adriatic Sea region), the Great Lakes and part of the East Coast of the U.S., Uruguay and southern New Zealand.

Most of winter lightning to tall structures belong to the upward lightning type [16,18,24,25]. Under winter storm conditions, the electric field over a tall structure will intensify, up to a point where an upward leader will emerge from the tip of the structure. The initial continuous current (ICC) that flows along this channel has a duration between tens to several hundred of milliseconds. The ICC may then be followed by one or more return strokes, generating what is called an upward lightning (UL). These return strokes are similar to subsequent return strokes in natural downward lightning [26]. It should be emphasised that conventional Lightning Location Systems (LLS) reliably detect downward lightning, but on the

contrarily, they miss a substantial fraction of UL, especially those having only an ICC component which is not followed by a return stroke [27]. Consequently, LLS observations substantially underestimate the risk of lightning damage [28,29,30].

Among all man-made tall structures, it appears that WT are those with a higher probability of initiating UL [28,31,32]. Compared to regular towers, the fast movement of these structures avoids the shielding effect caused by space charges, increasing the probability of the upward leader inception [17]. Besides, approaching downward leaders also lead to a rapid enhancement of the electric field and induced currents in grounded structures [33,34,35,36].

2.1 Objectives

While there is a fairly good understanding of the meteorological conditions favouring winter lightning in Japan, limited studies exist on the meteorological aspects of winter lightning to WT in other regions prone to winter lightning, like the north of the Mediterranean basin. This study provides new evidence analysing the meteorological conditions that favoured the occurrence of lightning to WT in different parts of Spain during snowstorm Filomena.

3. DATA AND METHODS

Lightning data for Spain during the Filomena snowstorm was obtained from the European LINET lightning location system (LLS) [37,38]. LINET-LLS employs the Time-of-Arrival technique to locate cloud-to-ground (CG) lightning strokes detected in the very-low-frequency range. LINET-LLS offers a location accuracy of around ~ 150 m, as verified by CG strokes to towers of known position [39].

Atmospheric data come from ERA5, the fifth-generation global reanalysis of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) [40]. ERA5 data has a spatial resolution of 31 km horizontally (available at a $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ latitude-longitude grid) and 137 levels vertically at hourly resolution. The use of reanalysis data, compared to the use of real atmospheric sounding measurements, provided data from a point of interest (latitude, longitude and time) that is closer to the event of interest than a sounding station does. In this case, we selected the points from the ERA5 grid closer to the windfarms (hereafter, WF) affected by lightning during Filomena.

ERA5 variables chosen to analyse meteorological conditions favouring lightning to WF are those that were found relevant in Stucke et al. [41] and Morgenstern et al. [42] for winter episodes. In particular, the study relies on temperature related variables like the height of the -10°C and -20°C isotherms and the 2 m temperature, skin temperature and 2 m dewpoint temperature. Besides, it also includes the most influential variables from cloud physics like the total column water vapor, convective precipitation, and surface pressure among others.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Overview of snowstorm Filomena

Storm Filomena was named by the Spanish *Agencia Estatal de Meteorología*, (State Meteorological Agency, AEMET) on 5 January 2021. Warnings were issued on the following days, and snowstorm Filomena finally affected Iberian Peninsula

between 8 and 10 January 2021, leaving an historically deep accumulation of snow in a large part of it (see Fig.1). The most intense snowfall occurred on 9 January, the same day winter lightning was observed in several WF.

The precursor depression for Filomena developed over the Atlantic Ocean in early January. Contrary to most of Northern hemisphere extratropical storms, this particular storm moved south, extending equatorward over western Europe and approaching the Sub-Tropical Jet which was located over North Africa and the western Mediterranean [43]. Such an unusual translation to subtropical latitudes resulted in a profound moistening. Subsequent advection of the now warm, moist perturbation to the mid latitudes of the Iberian Peninsula, where cold, polar air was flowing, resulted in a slantwise clash of two different air masses with an occluded front crossing Spain from southwest to northeast [44]. According to Zschenderlein and Wernli [45], the combination of the already cold temperature near the surface, the air mass boundary, and the dynamical forcing for ascent at this intense baroclinic zone were essential ingredients for this extreme snow fall event to occur.

4.2 Lightning during Filomena

Interestingly, in addition to the snow cover, Fig.1 shows that lightning also occurred during Filomena. Although most of lightning was oversea, lightning hotspots were observed in different regions across the Iberian Peninsula, such as Galicia, Asturias, Catalunya and Andalucía.

Fig. 1. Image of Copernicus Sentinel-3 from the 12th January 2021 showing the snow cover over the Iberian Peninsula with LINET lightning from the 8 January (orange) and 9 January (green)

A closer look showed that lightning flashes were sometimes clustered, mostly near wind farms (Fig 2). Clustering around tall human-made objects such as communication towers and WT, has already been reported during winter snowstorm episodes [25, 46, 47].

Table 1 summarizes the lightning activity related to WF during the 9th January 2021. Lightning affected twelve WF across Spain, in five Provinces and ten municipalities. Most lightning to WT were negative CG strokes ($-CG$), with relatively small peak currents. Studies on towers around the globe have reported a majority of $-CG$. Negative strokes are initiated by positive streamers [48,49,50], which require less intense electric fields compared to negative streamers, by about a factor of 2 [51].

Fig. 2. Lightning clustering around wind farms in Galicia (Mondoñedo) and Asturias (Capiexmartín, Bustellán, Curiscao-Pumar y Peña del Cuervo)

4.3 ERA5 variables

Instability indices presented in Table 2 shows no signs for strong moist convection, which depends upon large vertical motions and deep clouds, which in turn need large amounts of CAPE (Convective Available Potential Energy). Indeed, CAPE values in Table 2 are too small to explain the necessary vertical motions needed for the typical warm-season NIC electrification processes to take place. Instead, thunderstorm clouds in winter are lower-based and considerably shallower than in summer. In this type of clouds, charge separation is then no longer predominantly vertically related but horizontally (and needs no CAPE). Instead, it seems that high horizontal wind speeds and large vertical shear of the horizontal wind cause the charge separation. In wintertime, it is rather the collision between snowflakes and ice crystals and their subsequent separation along a slanted path that is thought to be responsible for the charge separation [20]. As winter clouds tend to be shallow but wide, lightning discharges will propagate long distances within these clouds. This means that electrical characteristics of lightning in winter differ from summer, e.g., in flash duration, direction, charge transfers; strength of the electric current; and the lightning electric field waveform [16, 52, 53, 54, 55]. According to Kitagawa and Michimoto [56] updraft speed (W_{max} in Table 2) should be above 3 m/s in order to allow charge separation in winter clouds. W_{max} values are above this threshold in the Galicia and Catalunya episodes, but not for Asturias.

Table 3 summarizes the analysed ERA5 variables related to temperature profiles and wind conditions. The height of the $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ isotherm is around 3500 m ASL in the Catalonia cases, and below 2500 m above sea level (ASL) in the Asturias and Galicia cases. Since the affected WF are at elevations between 500-1000 m ASL in Galicia and Asturias, this means the $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ isotherm is just 1500-2000 m above the WF. The $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ isotherm is below 5000 m ASL in the Catalonia cases, and below 4000 m ASL in the Asturias and Galicia cases. The Cádiz case (Andalucía) is in between. The criteria for winter lightning by Montanyà et al. [23], temperature below $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the 700 hPa height is fulfilled in the Asturias, Galicia and Andalucía episode, but not for Catalunya, where the temperature at 700 hPa was around $-6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The importance of temperature is explained by its influence on the height of the thundercloud's charge layer. The lower the temperature, the lower the cloud base, which brings the main electrification region closer to the tall structure tip. The reduced distance between the tall structure and the charged thundercloud then increases the electric field and eases the inception of UL

[19,57,58]. Low values on the height of freezing level and of wet-bulb freezing level (Table 2) suggest that precipitation is reaching surface as snow or at least as freezing precipitation in most of the WF around the time of UL occurrence.

Adhkari and Liu [7] associated cold season lightning events to those occurring when the two-meter surface temperature is colder than $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Besides, they defined thundersnow when the entire vertical temperature profile is below $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Our case studies are close to these conditions, although they are not always fulfilled.

Despite conductive environmental conditions, the presence of space charge produced by glow corona at the tip of tall towers can hinder the triggering of UL [34,59,60]. In fact, a strong wind is generally needed to remove the corona shield, clearing the way for initiation of an upward leader [16, 34, 61]. According to Mazur [62] this is the most probable explanation for the upward leader inception in the absence of the preceding nearby lightning flashes. Mostajabi et al. [63] conducted an analysis on UL, establishing a threshold of wind speeds higher than 12 m/s. In the case of WT, even if wind speed is not always above the threshold (Table 2), another factor must be taken into account: the effect of the blade rotation.

4.4 Effect of Blade Rotation

Observations by Montanyà et al. [17], Wang et al [47] and Wu et al. [64] among others supported the hypothesis that moving objects like WT can initiate stable UL leaders more easily than static objects like towers or power lines. WT experience a combination of two factors that aid the initiation of upward leaders. The first factor is that blade tips avoid the accumulation of self-produced space charge due to their rotation. The blades are therefore exposed to stronger local electric fields than static objects [65]. The second factor to consider is that blades are made with insulating composite materials which can accumulate charge.

5. CONCLUSIONS

While the general principles of lightning protection apply to all objects and systems, WT deserve special attention as they have a higher probability of being struck by lightning. In this regard, winter lightning has been recently introduced in the 2018 revision of the "Lightning Protection of Wind Turbines" standard IEC 61400-24. Still, more evidence is needed on the meteorological aspects favouring winter lightning to WT. The analysed episode of winter lightning to WT during snowstorm Filomena has shown that WF were specially affected.

This episode added evidence on the fact that conditions for winter lightning to WT can be reliably explained by meteorology. One of the most important variables is the height of the $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ isotherm. The closer the $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ isotherm is to the tall structure, the higher is the probability of inception of UL. Furthermore, a strong wind is needed to remove the corona shield of the tower tip, clearing the way for initiation of UL. In the case of WT, the moving blades can initiate stable lightning leaders more easily compared to other man-made tall structures like towers or power lines.

Table 1. Lightning related to Wind farms (WF). Wind Farm (Coordinates, Municipality, Province and Region). CG lightning counts and time of the first of the series on each WF. Peak current of the first and of the CG return stroke and maximum current of the series

Wind Farm	Date	Lightning		peak curr. (kA)		Latitude	Longitude	Elevation		Municipality	Province	Region
		counts	hour	first strol	max			m ASL				
Perelló Colladetes	9/1/2021	1	19:34:49	-10.1	-10.1	40.8955	0.6688	280		El Perelló	Tarragona	Catalunya
Gandesa-Batea	9/1/2021	10	19:28:41	-4.0	-26.3	41.0775	0.3908	465		Gandesa	Tarragona	Catalunya
Fatarella	9/1/2021	3	19:43:44	-4.5	-4.5	41.1568	0.4970	550		Ascó	Tarragona	Catalunya
Mora d'Ebre	9/1/2021	3	19:56:21	-11.4	-11.4	41.1389	0.5941	440		Ascó	Tarragona	Catalunya
Peña del Cuervo	9/1/2021	3	8:23:06	-5.3	-5.5	43.4665	-5.9872	560		Regueras	Asturias	Asturias
Curiscao-Pumar	9/1/2021	3	9:08:15	-6.5	-6.5	43.4848	-6.2953	800		Salas	Asturias	Asturias
Capiella Martín	9/1/2021	4	11:09:44	-7.5	-19.1	43.4339	-6.6151	970		Tineo	Asturias	Asturias
Bustellán	9/1/2021	3	9:11:04	-6.1	-10.6	43.3785	-6.3744	1000		Tineo	Asturias	Asturias
Mondoñedo	9/1/2021	3	11:27:08	-4.6	-24.9	43.4031	-7.4125	650		Mondoñedo	Lugo	Galicia
Peña Forcada	9/1/2021	1	13:19:06	6.4	6.4	43.1595	-9.1256	690		Camariñas	A Coruña	Galicia
Sierra da Loba	9/1/2021	1	8:13:22	-3.6	-3.6	43.3068	-7.9069	675		Guitiriz	Lugo	Galicia
Alcalá de Gazules	9/1/2021	1	16:22:18	-7.3	-7.3	36.4177	-5.7677	115		Alcalá	Cádiz	Andalucía

Table 2. ERA5 variables. Instability indices. Wind farm, time and peak current of the first CG return stroke at each WF. ERA5 variables. Convective Available Potential Energy (CAPE, J kg⁻¹), Convective Inhibition (CIN, J kg⁻¹), Lifted index, updraft speed (Wmax m/s), mixing ratio (g/kg) at the height of the surface-based parcel, height of freezing level (0°C) as a first available level counting from the surface. Units are m above ground level (AGL). Height of the freezing and wet-bulb freezing levels (m AGL), Convective precipitation (mm), total column water vapor (kg/m²).

Wind Farm	Lightning		Surface			Most unstable	Height	height of	Mixing	Conv.	Tot.Col
	hour	kA	CAPE J kg ⁻¹	CIN J kg ⁻¹	LI	WMAX (ms ⁻¹)	Freezing level (m AGL)	wet-bulb freezing level (m AGL)	Ratio g/kg	PPT (mm)	WV (kg/m ²)
Perelló Colladetes	19:34:49	-10.1	0	0.0	12.3	11.9	570	500	3.4	1.643	15.8
Gandesa-Batea	19:28:41	-4.0	1	0.0	12.8	8.0	20	20	3.4	1.462	14.2
Fatarella	19:43:44	-4.5	1	0.0	12.8	8.0	20	20	3.4	1.462	14.2
Mora d'Ebre	19:56:21	-11.4	0	-0.1	13.2	7.0	110	110	3.4	0.991	14.6
Peña del Cuervo	8:23:06	-5.5	0	0.0	9.8	0.0	440	327	0.5	0.042	7.6
Curiscao-Pumar	9:08:15	-6.5	0	0.0	9.8	0.0	440	327	0.5	0.042	7.6
Capiella Martín	11:09:45	-7.5	28	0.0	7.2	0.0	360	300	0.8	0.058	8.3
Bustellán	9:11:04	-6.1	0	0.0	8.8	0.0	370	260	0.4	0.049	7.5
Mondoñedo	11:39:40	4.0	16	0.0	5.4	5.6	300	250	3.7	0.005	7.1
Peña Forcada	13:19:06	6.4	137	0.0	0.7	16.6	900	700	4.8	0.008	9.5
Sierra da Loba	8:13:22	-3.6	0	0.0	5.4	0.0	300	190	0.7	0.000	6.8
Alcalá de Gazules	16:22:18	-7.3	89	0.0	-0.3	13.3	1000	875	4.9	0.017	12.1

Table 3. ERA5 temperature profile and wind related variables. Wind farm, time and peak current of the first CG return stroke at each WF. ERA5 variables: temperature related variables: 2 m temperature (°C), skin temperature and 2 m dewpoint temperature; Temperature at 700 hPa, Height of the -10 °C and -20 °C isotherms (m ASL), lifting condensation level (LCL, m AGL), Surface pressure (hPa) and wind at surface (m s⁻¹)

Wind Farm	Lightning		Temp		Td	Temp	Height		LCL		Sfc	Sfc
	hour	kA	2m (°C)	skin (°C)	2m (°C)	700 hPa (°C)	iso-10 (m)	iso-20 (m)	height (m)	Temp (°C)	Press (hPa)	Wind m/s
Perelló Colladetes	19:34:49	-10.1	2.2	2.6	1.3	-5.9	3526.2	4834.7	110	1.037	981.0	8.3
Gandesa-Batea	19:28:41	-4.0	0.2	-0.3	0.1	-6.2	3480.0	4807.5	20	0.017	959.4	6.7
Fatarella	19:43:44	-4.5	0.2	-0.3	0.1	-6.2	3480.0	4807.5	20	0.017	959.4	6.7
Mora d'Ebre	19:56:21	-11.4	0.7	0.1	0.6	-6.3	3454.0	4810.9	10	0.594	972.3	6.4
Peña del Cuervo	8:23:06	-5.5	2.5	3.1	-1.1	-13.8	2209.5	3839.5	450	-0.064	989.3	9.0
Curiscao-Pumar	9:08:15	-6.5	2.5	3.1	-1.1	-13.8	2209.5	3839.5	450	-0.064	989.3	9.0
Capiella Martín	11:09:45	-7.5	4.3	6.0	-0.1	-14.8	2190.0	3879.3	550	-1.506	977.2	12.7
Bustellán	9:11:04	-6.1	2.8	-0.8	3.9	-13.7	2217.0	3831.8	440	-0.507	982.4	12.0
Mondoñedo	11:39:40	4.0	4.3	4.2	-1.0	-13.9	2248.2	3796.0	650	-2.621	965.8	10.0
Peña Forcada	13:19:06	6.4	9.0	13.0	3.5	-13.2	2455.9	3811.6	690	1.324	1012.1	17.5
Sierra da Loba	8:13:22	-3.6	2.2	0.4	-0.2	-13.2	2441.2	3751.3	290	0.033	966.2	12.4
Alcalá de Gazules	16:22:18	-7.3	10.3	9.1	3.2	-10.3	2837.8	4136.2	900	0.785	985.8	3.6

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7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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LINET data is available only on request to the company.

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